

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: engr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	---	--

Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019

Md. Anowar Hossain
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
(engr.anwar@yahoo.com)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anwar@yahoo.com

Profile of Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

- <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
- <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
- <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
- <www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Keywords

Australian High Commissioner, Australian Visa Office, Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, RMIT University

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Ph.D Researcher (Enrolled)
RMIT University, Australia
M. Tech. in Textile Technology
(Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
E-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com
Mobile: +8801732681104

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head
Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Date: 04/12/2019

Australian High Commissioner
Dhaka, Bangladesh

Subject: Submission of Statement of Purpose for Studying at RMIT University under Simplified Student Visa Framework (SSVF) and RTP Stipend Scholarship of Australian Government

Dear Respected Officer,

Please seeking your kind attention that I have seven years and four months professional experience including three years and four months active teaching and research experience, fifteen publication in international peer reviewed journals, production job in textile industries and research & development job in technical textiles as well as completion Ph.D Research from RMIT university (expected) may vibrate my personal growth influencing the development of textile research area for both Bangladesh and Australia as my research on "Thermoregulated Smart Textiles" means a same garments can possible to wear both summer and winter season and/or other extreme weather conditions. Statement of Purpose for studying at RMIT University under Simplified Student Visa Framework (SSVF) has been attached with my visa application for your kind consideration where I have taken all preparation including "No Objection Certificate" from the present employer at City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh for the purpose of "Australian Student Visa".

I am ready to reply if your office has further requirements regarding my purpose of study at RMIT University although I have mentioned my details.

Thanking you

7.12.2019
Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
RMIT Student ID:3820066

Application ID: 2612540
RMIT Student ID: 3820066

Permanent Campus: Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Tel: 7746862, 7746863, E-mail: arcityuniversity@gmail.com
City Campus: 13/A Panthapath, Dhaka-1215, Tel: 9129923, 9143757, Web: www.cityuniversity.edu.bd

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Simplified Student Visa Framework (SSVF)
Statement of Purpose

Section 1

Personal Background:

In 100 words or less, tell us about you and your family. If you are married / separated, when did you marry / separate?
Do you have family living in Australia? If so, what do they do and what type of visa do they hold in Australia?

I am married since 28th August, 2018, beside my wife in my family I have mother, elder brother, elder sister. My wife is staying me in Dhaka city located my present working place behind City University. My elder brother is married who is doing job in a private company of Kuwait and my elder sister is also married and housewife. My elder brother and elder sister are self dependent and independently settled in their own profession. My mother name is Sakera Begam who is residing in our home town with my other family members. My father name is Md. Abdur Rashid (Late). He was a medical practitioner in my local area.
I have no family/relatives living in Australia.

Section 2

Family Background:

In 300 words or less, tell us about your spouse and children (if any).
Do your spouse and children intend to accompany you to Australia? What is your spouse's highest academic qualification and current occupation and what does your spouse intend to do in Australia?
Are you aware of visa condition and extra costs associated with bringing your spouse and/or children with you to Australia?

My spouse is completed Bachelor of Social Science from National University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. She has different professional training in Bangladesh like computer training, sewing, training, embroidery training. Presently my spouse is homemaker who is intended to accompany me in Australia and motivating myself to pursue Ph.D at RMIT University under the scholarship of Australian Government. She is also interested to introduce with new cultures and new environment in Australia.
RTP stipend scholarship will cover my extra cost associated with bringing spouse in Australia.

Anowar 09.12.2019
Application ID: 2612540
RMIT Student ID: 3820066

CRICOS Provider Code 00122A
RTO Code 3046 1/4 rmit.edu.au Issue date: November 2019 Ref: CRL

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Simplified Student Visa Framework (SSVF) Statement of Purpose

Section 3

Education and Employment Background:

In 300 words or less, tell us why you have applied for this program, what do you know about the program and its' cost, are you aware of additional costs associated with studying in Australia?
If this program is not related to your previous studies, why have you decided to change your career path?

Technical Textiles is my major study and research area when pursuing my Master of Technology in Textile Technology at Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, my professional experiences, my research experiences and related publications which are being directly matched with my research proposal entitled on "Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather condition" at School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Australia as well as approved by supervisor Professor Lijing Wang of same department.

All tuition fees and living cost associated with studying in Australia will be covered by RTP stipend scholarship of Australian Government.

Section 4

Gap in Study:

In 300 words or less, tell us about gaps in your study (if any). How long is the gap between your previous study and your intended study at RMIT, explain the reason for the gap.

The gap between my post graduation in Technical Textiles, University of Calcutta and my intended Ph.D in Technical Textiles study at RMIT University is four years and four months where the whole periods of gap has been purely utilized and deeply involved with research and teaching in different academic institutions in Bangladesh and professional collaboration with different prestigious international universities like Herriot Watt University, UK under Professor (Dr.) Danmei Sun, University of Calcutta, India under Professor (Dr.) AK Samanta, Jahangirnagar University under Professor (Dr.) Md. Nurul Absar by which way I have published fifteen research article in international peer reviewed journals as first and corresponding author and some of my paper is still under review process for publication in international peer reviewed journal.

Section 5

Why RMIT:

In 300 words or less, tell us why you have chosen RMIT over other universities in Australia (list other universities that you have researched and considered) and what do you know about RMIT?

RMIT University has a specialized field of research opportunity in technical textiles which is being matched with my specialization area of technical textiles studied in Master of Textile Technology (Technical Textiles), University of Calcutta, India. RMIT University has well-developed laboratory facilities in the field of technical textiles and a reputed team of researchers in the area of technical textiles leading by Professor Robert Shanks and Professor Lijing Wang who are the right person for supervising support/consulting support, developing and establishing my proposed project works in the level of high progression of research and development works.

Anowar
7.12.2019

Application ID: 2612540
RMIT Student ID: 3820066

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Simplified Student Visa Framework (SSVF) Statement of Purpose

Section 6

Australia and Melbourne:

In 300 words or less, tell us why you have chosen to study in Melbourne, Australia over other countries?
Please list other countries that you have researched and considered.

I was searching my well matched research university/technical textile based research university since 2015 after completion my M.Tech. in Technical textiles (By research) from department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India and my Ph.D research proposal was approved by professor Lijing Wang, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University after having effective coordination which is genuinely matched with my academic research career as well as way of my research goal.

I did research with different international universities like Herriot watt University, UK, Indian Institute of Technology, IIT, Kanpur, India, University of Calcutta, India and already I have fifteen research publication as first and corresponding author with the professor of enlisted universities.

Section 7

Education and Circumstances in Home Country:

In 200 words or less, tell us why you don't want to study in your home country?

Universities in Bangladesh is not offering Ph.D program under any department of textile engineering in Universities and my target research field is not matching with the universities of my home country although Bangladesh has universities to pursue B.Sc. and M.Sc. in textile engineering but there is huge lacking in research based degree and if I can do my Ph.D study from research graded laboratory, definitely I may have an opportunity to improve research and education for my country.

Section 8

Salary and Financial Benefit:

In 200 words or less, tell us about your salary expectation, how much do you expect your monthly salary to be when you return home with an Australian qualification? How does this compare to the salary you would receive if you studied in your own country?

Undoubtedly I will get a double /triple benefit with Australian degree comparing to study in my own country, when I will return home with Australian Ph.D from RMIT University and I will have an opportunity to work with high ranked universities in Bangladesh/Production unit of Technical Textiles based value added product/working facilities as consultant of textile industries/Govt. research organizations/entrepreneurship of technical textile based products as the research and innovation can be transferred to real life implementation as Bangladesh has huge opportunity in garments and textile sector. The expected monthly earning will be around 10,000USD after completion Ph.D but situation and performance may vibrate the specific earning and it can be told that the earning opportunity will be lighted in home and abroad after successful completion of Ph.D in my proposed research area.

Anwar 7.12.2019 Application ID: 2612540
RMIT Student ID: 3820066

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Simplified Student Visa Framework (SSVF) Statement of Purpose

Section 9

Career Progression:

In 300 words or less, tell us about your career aspirations and future plans after you graduate from this program.

After completion of my Ph.D program, definitely I will have a plan for doing Post Doctoral Research under any reputed University. I will deeply involved with research and innovation in my area of research collaboration with different applied based textile industries in home and abroad which may open a new door of product development in the area of thermoregulated smart textiles for special workers and extreme weather conditions and it will definitely minimize the difficulties with the surviving in extreme weather and adaptation of human body with different weather conditions.

Section 10

Post Study Plan:

In 100 words or less, tell us where you intend to permanently live and work when you complete your degree. If you intend to work temporarily in Australia once you complete your degree, which visa subclass you intend to apply for to work in Australia?

After my graduation from this program, absolutely I will involved in teaching and research career in my country where I am presently serving as lecturer but if I get any bright opportunity after having Ph.D from RMIT university, I have no limitation to work in any international research organization related to my research and study field which may be encouraged to work with research and invention as principal goal of my future career. After completion my Ph.D degree if I get any attractive offer from any university of Australia/research institution/related branches of my research/expertise area of my profession which may exceed the income of Bangladeshi offer/existing job I may decide to apply visa as per categories of skilled visa matched on the basis of my offer applicable by the norms of Australian High Commission during the time of visa application.

Declaration:

I declare that I have written this statement of purpose myself, I have not had assistance writing this and the information provided is my own work. I declare that I am a genuine student and a genuine temporary entrant to Australia. I also declare that I have sufficient funds to cover the cost of my tuition fees and living expenses for the duration of my studies.

Print your full name:

Md. Anwar Hossain

Student ID number: 3820066

Signed:

Date: 03/12/2019

Application ID: 2612540
RMIT Student ID: 3820066

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Publication List of my research career as proof mentioned in Section: 6

Papers Published in Peer Reviewed International Journal :

1. A. K. Samanta, Anwar Hossain, A. Bagchi, Kashmita Bhattacharya (2016) "Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric" in American Association for Science and Technology (AASCIT), USA, Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications 2016; 2(4): 25-34 <http://www.aascit.org/journal/jmsa> ISSN: 2381-0998 (Print); ISSN: 2381-1005 (Online).
2. Md. Anwar Hossain and AK Samanta (2018), Green Dyeing on Cotton Fabric demodulated from Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with green mordanting agent, Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing, USA, ISSN: 2637-4595, Published on May 9, 2018.
3. Md. Anwar Hossain, A K M Saiful Islam, and AK Samanta (2018), Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from *Swieteniamacrophylla* and *Musa acuminata* as Unpolluted Dyes and *Citrus. Limon (L.)* as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent, Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online), USA, ISSN: 25780271, Volume:3, Issue:2, DOI: 1031031/TTEFT.2018.03.000558, Published on June 19, 2018.
4. Hossain A, Ashis Kumar Samanta, Bhaumik NS, Vankar PS and Shukla D (2018), Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker, Journal of Textile Science & Engineering, USA, Volume 8, Issue 5, DOI: 10.4172/2165-8064.1000374, Received: August 18, 2018; Accepted: September 12, 2018; Published: September 17, 2018.
5. Md. Anwar Hossain, Ashis Kumar Samanta, Nilendu Sekhar Bhaumik, Padma S Vankar & Dhara Shukla (2018), Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distillated Organic Extraction of Organic *Tectona grandis* and *Azadirachta indica* with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants, International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering, Gavin Publisher, USA, Volume-2018, Issue-01, Accepted Date: 25 May, 2018, IJTSE-113. DOI: 10.29011/IJTSE-113/100013.
6. Anwar Hossain and Ashis Kumar Samanta, Cost Minimisation in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments, Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online), USA, ISSN: 25780271, Submission: July 16, 2018, Published: October 22, 2018.
7. Md. Anwar Hossain, (2015) "Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric" 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, 26th April, 2015, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay street), Kolkata-7000087, India.
8. Anwar Hossain, Danmei Sun, AK Samanta, Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions, Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology Weather Conditions, JResLit Journal of Science and Technology, JRL J Sci Technol. 2019; vol1-iss1: jst1005, Published: June 08, 2019.
9. Anwar Hossain and Samanta AK, Effect of Variation in Different Mechanical Setting of Draft Change Pinion in Trutzschler Carding, Machine for Cotton and Polyester Carded Slivers, Current Trends in Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering, Volume 4 - Issue 4 - July 2019, DOI:10.19080/CTFTTE.2019.04.555650.

4-12-19
Application ID: 2612540

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

10. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, A K Samanta, Uster analysis of cotton/polyester blended spun yarns with different counts, Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology , J Textile Eng Fashion Technol. 2019;5(4):213–218 Volume 5 Issue 4 – 2019, Accepted for publication.
11. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, AK Samanta, Md. Nurul Absar, Ferdous Ara Dilruba, A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural, Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre, International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering DOI: Volume 3; Issue 01 10.29011/IJTSE-126/100026, Accepted for Publication.
12. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, Uster Imperfections of 35% Cotton and 65% Polyester Blended Yarn for 40Ne, 50Ne and 60Ne Ring Spun Yarn, South Asian Research Journal of Engineering and Technology ISSN 2664-4150 (Print), Volume-1, Issue-2 (Aug-Sep, 2019), Accepted for publication.
13. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article, International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations, IJSEI Vol. 8, Issue 89, June, 2019, Accepted for publication.
14. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, A K Samanta, A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine, Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology, J Textile Eng Fashion Technol. 2019;5(5):235–240. DOI: 10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207.
15. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, Lijing Wang, Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions, Advanced Materials Research, Under final revision, October, 2019.
16. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, Md. Nurul Absar, A K Samanta: Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via *Psidium P. guajava* (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and *Citrus Lemon* (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent, Journal of Fibre and Polymer, Springer, Under review process.

Book Publications:

1. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology, Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2009.
2. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, Principle of garments production, Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010.
3. **Md. Anwar Hossain**, Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer, Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010.

 4.12.19
(Md. Anwar Hossain)
Application ID: 2612540
RMIT Student ID: 3820066

 4.12.19

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Supporting Documents of my foreign Ph.D offer as Proof of Statement of Purpose, Section: 06

02 November 2018

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

Dear Sir/Madam,

I am writing to confirm that Md. Anowar Hossain has been in contact with me regarding his PhD scholarship application and he has been offered a place for 2019 entry at the School of Textiles and Design, Heriot-Watt University.

Mr Hossain's proposed research project is "Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions", which is in line with my research interests. The aim of the research project is to explore techniques and manufacture processes for thermal regulated textiles and clothing systems, can be used as emergency suits worn by rescuers, oil and gas workers worn under the sea, etc.

I have over 25 years work experience in textile materials and engineering both practical and theoretical studies. I have been supervising Post-Doctoral Research Assistants and PhD students with various research projects, including functional fibres and smart polymeric materials, 2D/3D textile structures and engineering, offshore survival garment, modelling of textiles and property prediction etc. They are funded by various funding bodies such as UK Dstl/MoD, Scottish Funding Council, Textiles Future Forum, Oil and Gas Innovation Centre, Harris Tweed, Iron and Ocean Ltd. etc.

Mr Hossain and I had lots of conversations through email. I believe that he has very strong background and is the right person to pursue a PhD for the proposed project. We have all the facilities needed for his project and our research team at the school will support his research fully.

The concept and the workable procedures developed from the research can be transferred to industrial practice for developing performance suits. I would like to contribute my knowledge and expertise to the research project, being Mr Hossain's supervisor, to produce useful research output and save special professional' lives.

Sincerely yours

Danmei Sun PhD
Associate Professor in Advanced Textile Materials and Engineering
School of Textiles and Design
Heriot-Watt University, TD1 3HF, UK
Tel: +44 (0) 1896 89 2138
Email: D.Sun@hw.ac.uk

School of Textiles and Design
Heriot-Watt University Scottish Borders Campus Galashiels TD1 3HF United Kingdom
Telephone +44 (0) 1896 892133 Fax +44 (0)1896758965 www.tex.hw.ac.uk

Edinburgh Campus • **Scottish Borders Campus** • Orkney Campus • Dubai Campus
Heriot-Watt University is a Charity registered in Scotland, SC00027

4.12.18

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Page 1 of 2
Person ID: H00304057

06 February 2018

Md. Anwar Hossain Anwar
Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent Campus
Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka.
Birulia, Savar
Dhaka-1216
Bangladesh

Dear Md. Anwar,

Conditional Offer of a Place to Study at Heriot-Watt University

Qualification Title: Textiles, PhD (E119-TEX)
Location of Study: Scottish Borders

I have pleasure in offering you a conditional offer to study at this university. Details of your programme and tuition fee are quoted overleaf, together with details of the conditions you need to meet to secure your place.

You should reply to your offer online through the [Applicant Hub](#) by logging in, selecting "My Applications", and then using the "Reply to Offer" button.

If you have any queries, please feel free to contact us using the details provided below. We look forward to welcoming you as a student of Heriot-Watt University.

Yours sincerely,

Claire Johnston
Admissions Manager

Please direct correspondence to
Admissions Team
School of Textiles
Heriot-Watt University
Galashiels
TD1 3HF

Tel: +44 (0)1896 89 2156
Email: pgenquiries@tex.hw.ac.uk

04.12.2019
Application ID: 2612540
RMIT Student ID: 3820066

Heriot-Watt University
www.hw.ac.uk
Heriot-Watt University is a Charity registered in Scotland, SC000278

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

JResLit Journal of Science and Technology

Review Article

Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions

Anowar Hossain¹*, Danmei Sun², AK Samanta³

¹Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Bangladesh

²School of Textiles and Design, Heriot-Watt University, UK

³Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, University of Calcutta, India

*Corresponding Author:

Anowar Hossain, Department
of Textile Engineering, City
University, Bangladesh

Article History:

Published: June 08, 2019

Abstract

Smart textiles especially phase change materials in the stage of development process and still many important accomplishments are hidden with the success corner of related researchers due to unavailability of testing standards for clothing containing micro capsulated PCMs, compatibility of materials, matching with material properties and thermal performances, difficult to incorporate PCMs in clothing structure, polymeric shell puts dead weight to clothing, durability of PCM incorporated textile in repeated uses, higher price materials, toxicity which are the question marks for smart textiles. Challenges associated with PCMs while there can be significant advantages to using PCMs in certain encapsulation (as reviewed above), there are also a number of challenges regarding the research. Phase Change Materials (PCMs) are getting attention because these materials can provide regulation of wearer's body micro-environment and provide comfort in the temperature fluctuations during the physical activities and others like sports, space wears, undersea low temperature rescue, automobile, medical application, extreme weather, health & safety applications etc. Leading players in the PCM market are BASF (Germany), Rubitherm Technologies (Germany), and Enlropy solutions Inc. (U.S.), Outlast Technologies (U.S.). With the increased demand of smart textiles and comfort wears, the PCM market in textiles is bound to get steady growth in future.

Introduction

Figure 1: How PCM works

Smart textiles and its rapid economical growth

Technology is the seed of development for any country. Smart textiles is one of them which may create a revolutionary changes in economical and life style development. Development of Bangladesh economy is dependent much on exporting textile products, but only exporting of traditional readymade garments products can't vibrate the improvement of our economy as the international technology is going ahead very fast where Bangladesh government can concentrate to produce value added products and exporting such product can make as enforce development to make strong economy which can fight to build the country as developed country and positively Bangladesh textile product has a good reputation in world textile market where, without doubt, the exporting of smart textiles and clothing can make vital role as smart textiles and clothing have huge demand in developed countries like USA, UK, Canada, to survive their daily life, so research and development of such textile may have potential outcome in exporting.

Citation: Anowar Hossain. Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions. JRL J Sci Technol. 2019; vol1-iss1: jst1005.

© 2014 The Author(s). This open access article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 3.0 license

Accepted 4.12.19
Application ID: 2612540

1

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Supporting proof of my e-mail communication with Professor Lijing Wang, RMIT Supervisor mentioned in Section: 6 of SOP

- [Anowar Hossain](mailto:engr.anowar@yahoo.com) <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au

Dec 5, 2018 at 5:34 PM

Dear respected Sir,

Please may I request for evaluation of attached academic details as well as research proposal on smart textiles

Smart Textiles incorporated with encapsulated phase change materials containing latent heat for special workers and extreme weather conditions

Thanks for your kind attention

Md. Anowar Hossain

Master of Technology in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka.

Virus-free. www.avast.com

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

[Download all attachments as a zip file](#)

○

Research Proposal for RMIT.docx

70.5kB

○

CV_for_RMIT, Pdf.PDF

396.9kB

● **Lijing Wang** <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>

To: enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Dec 5, 2018 at 8:01 PM

Dear Anwar,

Thanks for contacting me. We have some research activities related to PCM. Hence, I can supervise your proposed program should you study with us. I suggest you consider:

1. We do not have manmade fibre laboratory. You may propose a different research task.
2. Active cooling should be a preferred approach.
3. It takes time to get familiar with FEM.

Kind Regards,

Lijing

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Hide original message

On Wed, 5 Dec 2018 at 20:35, Anwar Hossain <enr.anowar@yahoo.com> wrote:

Dear respected Sir,

Please may I request for evaluation of attached academic details as well as research proposal on smart textiles

Smart Textiles incorporated with encapsulated phase change materials containing latent heat for special workers and extreme weather conditions

Thanks for your kind attention

Md. Anwar Hossain

Master of Technology in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka.

Virus-free. www.avast.com

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- **Anowar Hossain** <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Lijing Wang

Aug 13 at 8:05 PM

Dear Respected Professor,

May I seek your kind attention to verify my academic profile enclosed in the attachment. I am highly motivated candidate to do Ph.D research in the area of your assigned proposal in any project as per suitability of your department although TWO PROPOSAL has been attached on smart textiles AS PER YOUR KIND SUGGESTION IN PREVIOUS SESSION-2018 AS YOU HAVE NO LAB FACILITIES OF MANMADE FIBRE PRODUCTION.

Thanks for your kind consideration to proceed myself as your research student in coming session of Ph.D admission.

Please advise me that what should I do if you have kind acceptance.

Best wishes

Md. Anowar Hossain

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

M.Tech. in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

University of Calcutta, India

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Show original message

[Download all attachments as a zip file](#)

○

CV_for_doctoral_program.PDF

406.7kB

○

Proposed_research_proposal_for_RMIT-2.PDF

255.3kB

○

Proposed_research_proposal_for_RMIT.PDF

371.7kB

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

○

Published paper on smart textiles.pdf

630.3kB

- **Lijing Wang** <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Aug 13 at 8:54 PM

Dear Anowar,

Thank you for sending the documents. I think your proposal may not be suitable for a PhD project, as I did not see the research gaps and questions. There are not many research tasks for new knowledge creation. However, you may submit a modified version for admission application. If you study with us, you have time to further develop your proposal. Note that I do not have any scholarship to support your study. RMIT University Scholarships are very competitive. If interested, you may find RMIT scholarship information from:

<http://www.rmit.edu.au/research/phds-and-other-research-degrees/scholarships-and-support/>

Good luck with your application.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Regards,

Lijing

Show original message

• **Anowar Hossain** <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Lijing Wang

Aug 15 at 12:39 AM

Dear Respected Sir,

A revised proposal on Thermoregulated Smart Textiles with Nano Conductive Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions has been forwarded for your kind attention.

May I seek your kind approval of my proposed research proposal to apply Ph.D for the session-2019.

Thanks

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
M.Tech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

**Md. Anowar Hossain, M.Tech. (Technical Textiles),
Department of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta
Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering
City University, savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.**

Show original message

o

Proposed_research_proposal_for_RMIT-2.PDF

346.6kB

- **Lijing Wang** <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Aug 15 at 8:30 AM

Dear Anowar,

I am fine with your research topic. You may apply for admission though I believe there is still room for highlighting the research gaps and questions and new knowledge creation in your proposal. All the best.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Regards,

Lijing

Show original message

• **Anowar Hossain** <enr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To:Lijing Wang

Aug 15 at 10:54 PM

Dear Respected Sir,

Thanks for your kind comments to develop my good proposal and accordingly I have found something new in the proposal where the topic and inside explanation has been edited slightly which may be a new theme of research.

Please I have attached edited proposal and Expression of interest (EOI) for your kind approval

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

which will have to upload separately in the first application process, EOI.

Please may I also seek your kind letter of agreement for supervision of my Ph.D research as per proposed entitled which will to upload as requirement in the first application process of EOI.

I have already started the first application process, EOI.

Thanks for your kind attention

Md. Anowar Hossain

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Show original message

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

[Download all attachments as a zip file](#)

○

Proposed_research_proposal_for_RMIT-3.PDF

273.2kB

○

Expression_of_Interest_for_RMIT.PDF

362.6kB

● **Anowar Hossain** <engr.anowar@yahoo.com>

To: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au

Aug 16 at 12:38 AM

Dear Sir,

Please another option of title has been forwarded for the confirmation of more suitable one comparing with earlier mail:

Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials and Synthetic Polymers

Thanks for your kind attention

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Md. Anowar Hossain

Show original message

-
-
-
-

- **Lijing Wang** <lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au>

To: Anowar Hossain

Aug 16 at 7:12 AM

Dear Anowar,

You may nominate me and Prof Robert Shanks as your research supervisor should you study with us.

Kind Regards,

Professor Lijing WANG, PhD

School of Fashion and Textiles

RMIT University

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Victoria 3056, Australia

Phone: 992 59414

Mobile: 0419 480 480

Email: lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au

Proof of my Publication work in starting stage in my research field with RMIT

Advanced Materials Research <9783035714319@scientific.net>

To: Mr. Md. Anowar Hossain

Nov 13 at 5:20 PM

Dear Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain,

Your manuscript "Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial Effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) Incorporated with Carbon Nanoconductive Materials for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions" was sent for revision after the external review.

We would be grateful you for the information about the end date of the revision of your manuscript.

Best regards,
Managing Director of journal,
Dr. Stanislav Kolisnychenko
Stanislav.Kolisnychenko@scientific.net

Md. Anowar Hossain, Lijing Wang, Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions, Advanced Materials Research, Under final revision, October, 2019.

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
Ph.D Researcher (Enrolled)
RMIT University, Australia
M. Tech. in Textile Technology
(Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
E-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com
Mobile: +8801732681104

Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka
Former Assistant Professor & Head
Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile
Engineering
Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong

Date: 07/12/2019

Australian High Commissioner
Dhaka, Bangladesh

Subject: Please consider my professional English Proficiency instead of formal IELTS

Dear Respected Officer,

I have the honor to draw your kind attention that I have around four years teaching experience in English medium instruction at B.Sc. engineering level, two years textile engineering education in M.Tech. level at foreign university, four years education in B.Sc. engineering level, regular international coordination for my continuous research and publication in international journal with international researcher & Journal editor as well as others professional experiences for dealing with international customers. Hence I am so much confidential to complete my Doctoral Program in English without any difficulties.

Please may I request to evaluate my visa application under consideration of my professional English Proficiency instead of having formal IELTS which may confirm my earlier reporting and starting my research at RMIT university.

Thanks

 7.12.2019

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain
RMIT Student ID:3820066

Application ID: 2612540
RMIT Student ID: 3820066

Permanent Campus: Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Tel: 7746862, 7746863, E-mail: arcityuniversity@gmail.com
City Campus: 13/A Panthapath, Dhaka-1215, Tel: 9129923, 9143757, Web: www.cityuniversity.edu.bd

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
---	--	--

References

- Hossain, A. (2020). A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen.
<https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360>
- Hossain, A. (2021a). Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01. <http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487>
- Hossain, A. (2021b). Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074>
- Hossain, A., Islam, A. S., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from *Swietenia macrophylla* and *Musa Acuminata* as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent. *Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 3(2), 1-8.
<https://crimsonpublishers.com/tteft/fulltext/TTEFT.000558.php>
- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. (2019). Effect of Variation in Different Mechanical Setting of Draft Change Pinion in Trutzschler Carding, Machine for Cotton and Polyester Carded Slivers. *Current Trends in Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering*, 4(4).
<https://doi.org/10.19080/CTFTE.2019.04.555650>
- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Cost Minimization in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments. *Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online), USA*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cost-Minimisation-in-Sample-Development-and-Process-Hossain-Samanta/ee6de04748b507cdec19cb7af66cfde0870a5b0d>;
<https://doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.04.000590>
- Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., Bhaumik, N. S., Vankar, P. S., & Shukla, D. (2018). Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distillated Organic Extraction of Organic *Tectona grandis* and *Azadirachta indica* with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 2018(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245102>
- Hossain, A., Sun, D., & Samanta, A. (2019). Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions. *JResLit Journal of Science and Technology*.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15079.62880>
- Hossain, M. A. (17 May 2023). *Anowar's Handbook on Application of Computer in Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23199.53923>
- Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology*, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>;
- Hossain, M. A. (2010a). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials II*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29667.94247>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241586>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010b). *Engineering of Textile Coloration* City University, Permanent Campus: Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854575>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11281.40801>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010c). *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer*, ISBN- 978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010d). *Principle of garments production*, ISBN-978-984-35-2884-1, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844918>
- Hossain, M. A. (2010e). *Production monitoring techniques of a knit composite industry*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854541>
- Hossain, M. A. (2015a, 26th April, 2015). *Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric* 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.26244>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844956>
- Hossain, M. A. (2015b). *Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments* [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India.]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854437>
- Hossain, M. A. (2019a). Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 8(89).

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11724.18561>; <http://www.ijsei.com/archive-88919.htm>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242756>

- Hossain, M. A. (2019b). Uster analysis of cotton/polyester blended spun yarns with different counts. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(4).
<https://doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2019c). Uster Imperfections of 35% Cotton and 65% Polyester Blended Yarn for 40Ne, 50Ne and 60Ne Ring Spun Yarn. *South Asian Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(2). <https://www.sciencegate.app/document/10.36346/sarjet.2019.v01i02.002>
- Hossain, M. A. (2020). My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020. Academic conference at PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33383.11680>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2021a). Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. *American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 31-47.
<https://doi.org/10.12691/materials-9-1-3>
- Hossain, M. A. (2021b, May 2023). Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination. Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2021c). Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), *Colorimetry* (pp. 1-22). IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.95699>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022a). Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination. *Defence Science Journal*, 72(3), 359-370. <https://doi.org/10.14429/dsj.72.17731>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022b, May 2023). Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background. Presented in humanities and social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson street, Brunswick, Vic-3056, Melbourne, Australia; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2022c). Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square*
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2022). Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. *Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Md. Anwar Hossain*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8196696>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023b). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2549022/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Anwar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29805.15844>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Anwar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anwar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936303>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Anwar's Handbook International Trade and Marketing Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25788.21120>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Anwar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13624.72966>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240342>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *Anwar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12923.49448>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *Anwar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15879.16801>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19654.04160>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35625.16486>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16822.88641>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Mechanical Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25368.78089>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Theory of Machine and Machine Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28724.22405>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *Anowar's Handbook on Environment and Safety Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36273.97126>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023p). *Anowar's Handbook on Fabric Structure and Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30821.37606>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240534>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023q). *Anowar's Handbook on Garments Manufacturing Technology*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27465.93280>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240547>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023r). *Anowar's Handbook on Industrial Economics*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34176.81925>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240589>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023s). *Anowar's Handbook on Machine Technology & Maintenance of Wet Processing Machineries*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22432.76802>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240660>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *Anowar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14883.02082>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Anowar's Handbook on Microprocessor, Robotics and Control Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26627.07204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023v). *Anowar's Handbook on Statistics for Engineer*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17714.17602>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023w). *Anowar's Handbook on Technical Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19391.89763>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241043>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023x). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Physics (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17294.74561>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241105>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023y). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Project Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35461.32480>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023z). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials I*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22537.62568>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aa). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing & Quality Control (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23166.77121>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241394>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023ab). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. [https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14778.16327](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14778.16327;);
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ac). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. [http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34071.96169](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34071.96169;);
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241183>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19896.52484>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ae). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29857.99683>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023af). *Application for promotion as Professor (Textile Engineering) and/or right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV), publications and teaching experiences under the promotion act of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; supported by the act of University Grants Commission of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh.*
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ag). Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds. 5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023;
[http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282](http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282;); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>,
Valencia, Spain.
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ah). Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds. Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23969.17766>,
Rome, Italy.
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ai). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022].
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023aj). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination*, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ak). Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2686707/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023al). *Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023am). Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023an). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ao). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when self-studying of student/researcher is an automatic contribution for national and worldwide development without getting money. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2831203/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ap). *Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112431>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aq). First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks. In: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ar). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind*. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, enr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023as). *Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Polymer Science & Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31974.80969>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

<p>Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia (Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship) Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles) Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles, Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007 Visit Profile http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287 https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT</p>	<p>Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India) Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264</p>	
--	---	--

- Hossain, M. A. (2023at). Md. Anwar Hossain, Video presentation of Anwar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2023au). *My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on "camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds"* [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021].
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023av). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3)*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966475>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aw). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933678>,
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ax). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933704>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ay). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>;
- Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ba). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bb). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bc). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023be). Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research*, 7(1), 67-71. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection* [Biodata].
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848583>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bh, 10-11 July 2023). An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm. Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology" (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>, Paris, France.
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bi). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bj). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University*; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bk). *Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anwar Hossain*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8196694>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain as per office order of RMIT University, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8273064>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bl). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anwar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate*

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. .

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8194679>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bn). Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182530>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bo). Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182709>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8273582>

Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023bq).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>

Hossain, M. A. (2023br). Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics) (Australia Patent No.

R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions. *School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia* (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). UV-Visible-NIR Camouflage Textiles with Natural Plant Based Natural Dyes on Natural Fibre against Woodland Combat Background for Defence Protection. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2126958/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). UV-Visible-NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bx). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A., Absar, M. N., & Samanta, A. K. Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent, submitted for publication. .

Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne,
Australia
(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTEch in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Consultant (Fashion & Textile Manufacturing, Cost Minimization
in Textile Industry, Textile Coloration, Defence Textiles,
Technical Textiles, PhD Researcher, Crime Protection, Crime
analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in
Higher Education), Motivational speaker & writer since 2007
Visit Profile
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

Professor, Professor Dr. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering; and
Former Assistant Registrar, Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator, Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka,
Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (R&D), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur,
Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of
Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh & India)
Contact: enr.anwar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Absar, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>
- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A. K., NS, B., PS, V., & Shukla. (2018). Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker. *Journal of Textile Science & Engineering*, 8(5), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000374>
- Md. Anwar Hossain, A. K. S. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240. <https://doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>
- Samanta, A. K., Hossain, A., Bagchi, A., & Bhattacharya, K. (2016). Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications*, 2(4), 25-34.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16757.35048>

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Anwar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019, School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia, enr.anwar@yahoo.com